

Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan

Janita Van Dyk, July 9, 2025, Version 3.1

DEC Overview

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Glossary

TERM	DEFINITION	TERM	DEFINITION
CA	Consortium Agreement	KER	Key Exploitable Result
D[No.]	Deliverable [No.]	KPI	Key Performance Indicators
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication	PC	Project Coordinator
EC	European Commission	T[No.]	Task [No.]
GA	Grant Agreement	WP[No.]	Work Package [No.]

Consortium

ROLE	NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
Coordinator	University of Durham	UDUR	UK
Partner	Atlantic Technological University	ATU	Ireland
Partner	Barcelona Supercomputing Center	BSC	Spain
Partner	City, University of London	CITY	UK
Partner	Fundació Alícia	FA	Spain
Partner	Institut LYFE	LYFE	France
Partner	Instituto Superior Técnico	IST	Portugal
Partner	Roskilde University	RUC	Denmark
Partner	University College Cork	UCC	Ireland
Partner	University of Alicante	UA	Spain
Partner	University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo	UNISG	Italy
Partner	University of Milan	UMIL	Italy

Legal disclaimer

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Executive Summary

The present document is D10.2 “Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Plan” under the task of WP10: SERVING A (for months 1–18) and for revision by WP11: SERVING B (for months 19–36) as Deliverable 11.1.

The report describes the design of the project’s communication tools, such as visual identity, communication materials, digital or media platforms, and project templates. The report also outlines the dissemination activity plans for the project, strategies for exploitation, and how impact indicators will be measured and assessed.

All the above is completed by the University of Durham (UDUR) with consortium member input.

1 Introduction

RELISH (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage) is a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project that offers a pathway to put into practice culinary recipes and food culture as cultural and digital tools to strengthen a crucial aspect of EU's common cultural heritage. Through an innovative and systematic approach to the understanding and use of traditional EU recipes via digital and AI-powered technology, it embarks on the production of a visual and verbal food storytelling web platform that aims to mediate social cohesion, reinforce EU cultural heritage transmission both at home and abroad through education and public engagement, while addressing sustainable practices in the home kitchen and the EU hospitality sector.

Durham University (UDUR) leads Work Package 10: SERVING (A) and Work Package 11: SERVING (B) involving Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation. Its objectives are as follows:

- Boost the visibility of the project's approach, activities, and results throughout the life of the project by designing and employing appropriate communication tools to reach and engage with different target audiences.
- Ensure the future uptake and use of the project's results during and after the project through planning and implementing targeted dissemination actions aimed at end-users and key stakeholders to enhance acceptance of project results.
- Facilitate efficient exploitation of the results by actively handling Intellectual Property (IP) issues, the dissemination of guidelines, recommendations, and specific information produced by RELISH and aimed at EU policymakers, businesses, associations, and other stakeholders, as well as the general EU public.

1.1 Description of the document

This is the first version of the DEC Plan for D10.2. It describes and reports on the tasks completed or ongoing for T10.1 "Communication tools and outreach campaign" and T10.2 "Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) Plan. This document explains the methods and strategies to reach present and future stakeholders.

To plan for exploitation, a preliminary list of exploitable results is identified and methods to maximise impact outlined. These include current and planned strategies, identified stakeholders the project seeks to build or attract, various communication and dissemination tools that will be used, and outlining preliminary issues and opportunities to be assessed and reported on for D11.1.

1.2 WPs and tasks related to the deliverable

The DEC Plan, strategies, and tasks are completed by UDUR in WP10 & 11, with input and contributions available to all interested project partners. This deliverable falls under the task for T10.2, the completion and submission of the DEC Plan for Months 1–18 of this project.

This deliverable also reports on the ongoing and completed work of **T10.1 “Communication tools and outreach campaign,”** in which UDUR supports widespread recognition of the project through a corporate identity (including logo, colours, fonts, key visuals, and a website containing information on the project’s key activities, intended impacts, partners, and stakeholders). It will also determine and use relevant social media and communication tools to boost the project’s public visibility.

Completion of D10.2 also encompasses T10.3 and T10.4 in furthering the communication and dissemination tools and exploitation strategies related to public policy, building stakeholder awareness and engagement, and issues related to IP protections and industry/policy potentials:

- **T10.3 “Dissemination, capacity-building and policy input”**—UDUR will lead development in engagement strategies in conjunction with all WP Leads to enable effective outreach to stakeholders with a mix of face-to-face, online, and social media channels.
 - Working collaboratively with WP Leads, UDUR will test routes to reach wider audiences and promote their involvement and understanding of the technical, financial, environmental, and societal effects of the RELISH project.
 - An important focus of the dissemination activities will be the involvement of regulatory and public bodies through workshops and meetings with other WPs.
 - UDUR will coordinate scientific dissemination and output as partners have plans to publish in scientific publications or present findings in scientific conferences.
- **T10.4 “Exploitation of results and IP management”**—UDUR will be responsible for managing the exploitation of project results and IP, in accordance with the defined Consortium Agreement (CA). All partners will provide advice and feedback regarding the decisions to be made.
 - Activities will include the management of the evolution of the Consortium Agreement, definition of the IPR protection and publication strategies, and authorisations for public dissemination of sensitive results or information.

2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

Following the European Commission's Glossary of terms,¹ RELISH understands “communication” and “dissemination” as follows:

COMMUNICATION

“[A] strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. [...]

The purpose of the communication activities is to make the research activities known to multiple audiences (in a way that they can be understood by non-specialists) and the activities must address the public policy perspective of EU research and innovation funding, by considering aspects such as (i) transnational cooperation in a European consortium (i.e. how working together has allowed to achieve more than otherwise possible) or (ii) scientific excellence or (iii) contributing to competitiveness and to solving societal challenges.”

DISSEMINATION

“[T]o make the results of a project public (— by any appropriate means other than protecting or exploiting them, e.g. scientific publications).”

2.1 Objectives

Communication aims at the following goals:

- To raise public awareness about the project, its expected results and impact within defined target groups
- To make the project a valid source of information
- To create synergies and exchange experience with projects and groups active in the same topic, to join efforts and maximise common potential

Dissemination aims at reaching the following goals:

- To create public awareness and generate scientific interest

¹ “Glossary,” European Commission: EU Funding & Tenders Portal, n.d., <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>.

- To directly involve stakeholders that could help bridging the gap between the RELISH concept and its market application
- To maximise the impacts of the project achievements
- To disseminate the fundamental knowledge, the methodologies and technologies developed and tested during the project
- To facilitate cooperation with other projects

2.2 Rationale and framework

RELISH's goal is to transition and create innovative pathways for reinterpreting **recipes** from technical instructions into cultural and digital tools. In relation to communication and dissemination, models and frameworks for a “transition” and/or innovation should be appropriate and relevant in timeline planning (see 2.3).

RELISH understands communication and dissemination strategies as encompassing “alliance building” through transition activities that create and sustain relationships, engagement and collective investment through the life of the project.

Alliance building is commonly one which encompasses difference, i.e. that stakeholders and potential users might have different investments, needs, and uses for the project's findings, and that its object, “the recipe,” is differently understood and thus has the capacity to be more diversely valued. Encompassing alliance building is the project's work to transition common understandings of recipes as technical instructions into digital and cultural tools for innovation, sustainability, and heritage. As a transition strategy, RELISH will develop the framework of “boundary objects,” defined as “how ambiguous artefacts (boundary objects) can be deliberately employed by actors to drive transitions through bridging conflicting logics without constraining their diversity.”² Thus, RELISH employs this framework to build alliances through its communication and dissemination activities.

RELISH breaks down these strategies as the following:

Stage 1. Person-Centred Introductions

RELISH is both a project and a set of social and institutional partnerships. Key to building awareness of the project's stakes and goals is to also introduce those already invested in the project, i.e. the consortium members and their representative communities. Communication and dissemination activities will focus on providing researcher biographies, collaborative settings, institutional

² Manuel Franco-Torres, Briony C. Rogers, and Rita M. Ugarelli, “A Framework to Explain the Role of Boundary Objects in Sustainability Transitions,” *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions* 36 (September 2020): 34, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2020.04.010>.

contexts and preliminary perspectives on the role of recipes in heritage, sustainability and innovation interests.

Stage 2: Enrolling Stakes and Problems

In initial research activities, differing and/or unanticipated stakes and issues related to the role of recipes in heritage, sustainability, and innovation are not foreclosed but instead explored and invited. Communication and dissemination activities will thus focus on inviting various stakeholders' engagements and perspectives through various platforms (such as social media).

Stage 3: Mutual Learning and Investment

Communication and dissemination activities will focus on building capacity for various stakeholders to recognise issues and problems they might not have been able to identify before, and to evaluate how consortium members frame and analyse these problems in project activities and publications. Strategies will focus on building investment in learning and collaborating with situated or specific aspects of project activities.

Stage 4: Supporting and Building Stakeholder Communities

One desired result for RELISH is to build situated or networked communities of various stakeholders, including guardians (e.g. knowledge-keepers, researchers, culinary professionals), mediators (educators, RELISH partners, policymakers) and emerging adults (young, often mobile, and previously ambivalent food decision-makers). Across both RELISH's platform development and communication and dissemination activities, an "end-user" base is not always captured but produced. Thus, outreach activities in this section will involve activities which put extant and emerging stakeholders into contact through workshops, pedagogical/methodological training, and prototype/beta testers.

2.3 Timeline

A timeline gathering all key communication and dissemination activities related to the framework stages outlined in 2.2 is provided and will be updated throughout the project, with revisions/amendments updated for D11.1.

STAGE 1: M1-9

Activities aimed at introducing RELISH project and partners via:

- RELISH logo design
- Website launch and "RELISH Digest" (blog) for visual presence and document project activities, interviews, and think pieces

- Setting up and populating social media accounts (Bluesky, Instagram, YouTube) to build follower base, comment and engage with food studies and food industry stakeholders, produce frequent posts featuring RELISH consortium partners
- Initial press releases (including template) on institutional partners' grant acquisition and gatherings
- Creating presentation, report, business cards, and letterhead templates
- Initiating collaborative series and posts with podcasts and magazines (e.g. *The StopGap's* "Expiration Dates" series)
- Promotional videos featuring interviews and project framing
- Conference presentations and invited talks on preliminary project framing
- Exploitation workshop at first consortium meeting

STAGE 2: M10-19

Activities aimed at inviting perspectives and values in RELISH project and partners via:

- Invited and open workshops/conferences on recipe methodologies
- Pilots and ERASMUS+ outreach with partner institutions to encourage survey respondents and workshop participants
- Circulating social media polls, Q&As and outreach Digest posts on interviewing non-consortium member stakeholders (especially "culinary guardians"; see Table 1)
- Conference presentations and invited talks on ongoing or completed project activities and findings
- With RUC, FA, and ATU, conducting and dissemination workshops and seminars with international/European students in developing methodologies regarding food and storytelling

STAGE 3: M20-29

Activities aimed at mutual learning and project output dissemination by RELISH project and partners via:

- Initiating and producing two out of three planned seasons of a RELISH podcast series
- Conference presentations and invited talks on ongoing or completed project activities and findings

- Exploitation workshop for consortium members to refine communication and dissemination strategies and evaluate potential impact and responsibilities
- Updated and revised DEC Plan
- Research publication draft submissions for OA publications (research journals and academic presses)
- With UMIL, LYFE, FA, RUC, and ATU, circulating preliminary reports, teaching tools, and guidelines on recipes and culinary heritage via informational Digest posts and social media channels
- Promotional videos developed and circulated in collaboration between UNISG and UDUR, as well as other informational recorded interviews and guides
- One-day regional conference on RELISH activities organised by UDUR
- Hosting a booth and talk series at Terra Madre – Salone del Gusto (2026) and mid-point consortium meeting in Pollenzo (originally scheduled M18 but rescheduled to M20 to maximise dissemination and communication opportunities for RELISH)

STAGE 4: M30-36

Activities aimed at supporting and building stakeholder communities by RELISH project and partners via:

- Producing and concluding the 3rd and final season of RELISH podcast
- EU policy roundtable to initiate conversation on RELISH research and findings on issues of IP, AI, and sustainability related to culinary heritage and recipes
- EU policy recommendations on issues of IP, AI, and sustainability related to culinary heritage and recipes
- Research publication draft submissions for OA publications (research journals and academic presses)
- Consortium members' conference presentations and invited talks on completed or ongoing project activities and findings as reported to WP10/11
- Selected interviews and educational videos (conducted by CITY) with food professionals to be circulated on RELISH platforms (website and social media)
- With UA, final consortium meeting and community/institutional press releases on RELISH output

2.4 Stakeholders and target audiences

RELISH will build and capture a series of stakeholders and communities related to recipes as cultural and digital tools for innovation, sustainability, and heritage. We have categorised five main stakeholder groups and target audiences, which encompass sub-sections of users and disseminators. In Stages 1–3, the primary targeted stakeholders are: “Culinary Guardians” and “Mediators.” In Stage 4 we focus primarily on building and enrolling “Mediators,” “Emerging Adults,” and “Policymakers” stakeholder communities. An additional fifth group is located here, that of “Citizens and Society,” encompassing broader beneficiaries after the project’s completion.

Similarly, each stakeholder group and audience will be invited to engage in, respond, or receive particular forms of communication related to their anticipated values, stakes, and level of familiarity with food research and culinary heritage.

Table 1: Description of RELISH Stakeholder Groups

STAKEHOLDER GROUPS	ROLES	COMMUNICATION MESSAGING
Policymakers	<p>EU policy- or lawmakers working on issues related to regulating, recognising and increasing protections for Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH), food sustainability issues and involving younger generations in food heritage and culture programs.</p> <p>Invested in creating more sustainable and innovation solutions to maintaining and developing valuable food forms and meanings in Europe.</p>	<p>While many protections for heritage or culturally meaningful foods often involve protection, they can insufficiently recognise recipes and transformation involved in how food moves, changes and is regulated or protected.</p> <p>By comparing hard law (IP protections and patents) and soft law (e.g. Geographic Indications) instruments, as well as new developments in AI/LLM integration in food recipe development, RELISH will provide recommendations on opportunities, barriers and limitations regarding recipes reflecting changing legal developments related to food and sustainability protections. These recommendations will help advise on how to integrate disadvantaged populations and commercial or industry roles.</p>
Emerging Adults	<p>Young generation of often mobile people living in Europe who may be ambivalent, interested but insecure, or avoidant about food knowledge or technical skills pertaining to culinary heritage and recipes.</p>	<p>Food is inextricably linked to identity, but with more choices, mobility struggles or opportunities, and increasing sustainability and climate problems, who young people are and what they eat will be increasingly troubled or challenged.</p>

	<p>Accessing and using culinary tools often different from previous generations (social media, online blogs, international workshops or tours, and/or unfamiliar marketplaces and restaurants). Variously invested in how their futures and identities are reflected in the forms that cuisine and recipes take.</p>	<p>RELISH provides proactive tools for young people to see themselves and their values reflected in food heritage and communities in inclusive and empowering formats. The platform will provide educational, technical/pragmatic, and future-oriented strategies to navigate recipes, food access, and ethical or economic decision-making.</p>
<p>Culinary Guardians</p>	<p><u>Knowledge Guardians</u>: “Keepers” of culinary knowledge and invested experts involved in collecting, researching, and/or using culinary knowledge and recipes. For example: researchers, archivists, collections owners.</p> <p>Reflective of existing consortium members and institutional centres preliminarily seeking to operationalise knowledge about recipes and food in culinary heritage, sustainability transitions, but may not yet have holistic or user-oriented tools to reach relevant audiences.</p>	<p>Research collections, analyses, and interdisciplinary collaboration with recipes are currently insufficient/not adequately supported to assess and respond to emerging climatological, mobility, and identity issues.</p> <p>RELISH will provide opportunities to engage in open sharing of culinary recipe data and analysis, avenues to reach new audiences via novel integration and use to computing, design, historical, and social resources, as well as offering guidelines, methodologies for teaching, and opportunities to collaborate on testing and developing frameworks.</p>
	<p><u>Professional Guardians</u>: Agencies, industries and professionals involved in collecting and/or using culinary knowledge and recipes. For example, food professionals (chefs, restaurateurs), think tanks, food and recipe (including AI) software developers.</p> <p>Invested in protecting, diversifying, and innovating food services and products with emerging tools (e.g. AI) and legal recognition.</p>	<p>Through RELISH’s platform and collaborations, we facilitate access and collections to recipes that can provide opportunities for food professionals and industry experts to expand their demographic and user base to encompass knowledge, cultural communication and food access for new clients and consumers.</p>
<p>Mediators</p>	<p><u>Cultural Mediators</u>: those working between institutional and/or industry guardians and “end-users” or other stakeholders in organising and sharing culinary heritage and recipes. For example: community organisers, public-facing food knowledge communicators, senior family members, social media influencers, and others.</p> <p>Invested in translating expert knowledge, family food histories, and inaccessible food professional spaces</p>	<p>RELISH provides holistic and interconnected access to recipe collections, analysis, pedagogical guides, and opportunities to reflect situated or local needs in the design and development of open access publications and digital tools.</p>

	to wider, minority, disadvantaged or unaware publics.	
	<p><u>Educational Mediators</u>: those working between institutions/industries in translating culinary knowledge, heritage and recipe interpretation in higher education. For example, professors, researchers.</p> <p>Invested in bridging expert knowledge, food histories and collections and research recommendations to wider, minority, disadvantaged or unaware publics.</p>	Food recipes, collections, and research can be inaccessible and/or fragmented. Engaging with them tends to invite specific reflections rather than interconnected issues. In general, recipes are undervalued, commonly regarded as instructional or textual resources, and could be better integrated into policy, sustainability research, or innovation tools.
Citizens and Society	<p>Broadly encompassing private individuals in Europe, inclusive of visitors, migrants, residents, and private enterprise.</p> <p>Those who may be interested in or seek knowledge or experiences related to recipes that relate to sustainability diets, typicity, heritage, local food, transnational food exchange, and/or AI/IP issues.</p>	<p>Recipes are more than technical instructions; they are texts, family or regional expressions of history, social identity, indicators of movement and change, express hierarchies of expertise and value, and forms of innovation.</p> <p>Related to Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH), it is not only the form of food but the means that it is expressed, taught, and ingredients it encompasses that could be better integrated into society, community, and industry projects. RELISH assists in bringing food knowledge regarding recipes and heritage to wider publics.</p>

2.5 Impact assessment

By implementing this DEC Plan, RELISH aims to communicate relevant outcomes and opportunities to each of the target groups, as well as to attract their interest and engagement, which will increase the overall impact of the project.

To evaluate the preliminary and ongoing impact or engagement in RELISH activities across these five stakeholder groups, quantitative indicators and other numerical or qualitative metrics were outlined where applicable. Numerical targets are included to set goals, as well as assess and monitor the project's impact over time. The proposed metrics can be categorised as:

- Quantitative indicators such as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and online metrics
- Qualitative indicators such as the promotion of an active, engaged community, press coverage, conference panel engagement, network building, and long-term influence

Metrics will be reviewed periodically by the consortium members at the end of each Stage.

2.5.1 Quantitative indicators (KPIs)

Table 2: Description of RELISH KPIs

INSTRUMENTS	DESCRIPTION	INDICATORS
Visual Identity	Consistent and professional visual identity	Logo, brand identity palette
Website	Regularly updated website (relisheu.org) with a blog, the RELISH Digest, to regularly report on partner activities and opportunities	200 visits per month (total of up to 10,000 visitors)
Communication kit	Hardcopy communication material for RELISH events and presentation template	1 PowerPoint and Google Slides template 1 banner 1 letterhead template 1 report template
Bluesky	Posting on social media in the form of original stories, entries, replies, and reposts	10 original posts per month 5 interactions with followed accounts or followers per week 500 followers
Instagram	Posting on social media in the form of original stories, entries, replies, and reposts	10 original posts per month 20 original Instagram stories per month 5 interactions with followed accounts or followers per week 500 followers
Videos	Videos to disseminate RELISH activities on social media, RELISH website, and YouTube	4-5 videos >200 viewers each
Press Releases	Regular updates on RELISH partner activities distributed on institutional partner and news outlet channels	1 every four months
Podcast	Three seasons of a RELISH podcast (Title TBD) featuring partner interviews, recipe-related educational content, and project updates	3 seasons x 6 episodes each (25-30 min per episode) 100 listeners/episode
Publications	Publications submitted to peer-reviewed and open-access journals and academic presses	2 volumes >5 research articles

Conference participation	Conference presentations/invited talks at regional and discipline-specific associations on RELISH frameworks, project, and findings/output	2 presentations every year
Exhibitions and association meetings	Hosting or participating in an exhibition or creating a series of workshops, tastings, seminars, and/or outreach	2 events
Policy recommendations and briefs	Meeting with EU policymakers and food industry stakeholders to workshop activities and recommendations and produce final reports for potential exploitation/implementation	2 workshops or meetings 2 reports

2.5.2 Qualitative indicators

Qualitative indicators encompass the perceived and experienced engagement with and impact of the project through individual or collective assessments and meeting reports related to:

Active and Engaged Online and Participant Community

Across social media channels, online communication tools, and workshop/seminar participation, RELISH will document and discuss with relevant consortium members the degree of communication, excitement, repeat engagement, and reposting/sharing of RELISH communications, reports, activities and posts.

Press and Association Coverage

Promoting RELISH events, activities, and press releases at key stages of the project (including conferences, consortium meetings, exhibitions, and task/deliverable completion months) will provide opportunities for press/media to initiate their own reporting or coverage in the form of news articles and association-managed spotlight pieces.

Conference Engagement and Network Building

RELISH will create a network directory over the course of the project, to be updated with interested conference attendees, prior partnerships or associations, and institutions to build an institutional and industry early-adopter base for disseminating or valorising RELISH's activities, findings and output.

Long-term Influence:

Difficult to anticipate in advance, across the four stages of the DEC plan, UDUR and relevant consortium members will review key impact areas that will extend beyond the life of the project with regards to the platform development, update, and future research, policy, legal, or youth stakeholder collaborations with consortium members' findings, methods, guides, and other output.

3 Communication Tools

Communication tools encompass accessible, professional, and youth-oriented platforms and visual identities that represent a clear image for all RELISH consortium members and stakeholders.

3.1 Visual identity

The RELISH visual identity design is premised on bright and non-literal food elements and colours, flexibility in use, and clear typography. The spoon/ladle element integrated in the logo will also be used through communication in the form of watermarks or overlays and emojis (🥄) used in social media to represent the project. Whenever possible, this visual identity will be used across all RELISH outputs, publications, and social media platforms.

3.1.1 Project logo

A distinct, memorable logo was designed for RELISH's visual identity. The logo highlights action and collaboration through the movement of the "scooping" ladle/spoon, generating flow with the treatment of the "R," and is inclusive of food utensils common cross-culturally to many eaters in Europe. Slight texture/speckling is included to soften the logo.

Figure 1: RELISH Project Logo - Master

LOGO VERSIONS

The logo is adaptable to digital and print use, with negative treatment for use on dark backgrounds, as well as black and white mono treatments.

Figure 2: RELISH Logo Treatments

3.1.2 Visual design colours

Colours were selected to provide bright tones, strong contrast, and communicate energy and warmth.

Figure 3: RELISH brand colours

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3.1.3 Typography

Typefaces selected for publications were selected for their variety of weights, free licensing available through Google Fonts and Microsoft, and to allow for a combination of serif and sans-serif treatments for titles, subheadings, and body text.

Lato and Merriweather (Serif) were chosen in specific as complementary typefaces. They will used consistently across all RELISH public-facing output and reporting.

Figure 4: Selected typefaces for RELISH project

3.2 Website

WP10's first deliverable (D10.1) was the creation and launching of a RELISH website, relisheu.org. The website is a central communication, dissemination, and repository tool to feature the project framework, rationale, activities, and any forthcoming opportunities.

An additional element of the website is a "blog," titled the RELISH Digest, which reports on and republishes events, activities, and interviews with project partners and stakeholders.

The website was designed on WordPress to feature visuals, text-heavy, or narrative sections, and track user traffic and clicks through the site. Key to its design was flexibility to update pages and posts during the granting period, as well as optimising screen reading for phone or tablet.

Figure 5: RELISH website design

3.3 Social media

RELISH will use several social media platforms to communicate and disseminate visual, video, and textual information and engagement with online audiences. We selected Bluesky ([@relish-he.blsky.social](https://bsky.app/profile/@relish-he.blsky.social)) for primarily textual posts, Instagram ([@relish_he](https://www.instagram.com/relish_he)) for images and video, and YouTube ([@RELISH-EU](https://www.youtube.com/@RELISH-EU)) to distribute and host promotional content, collaborations, interviews, workshop proceedings, and future podcast episodes.

3.4 Communication materials

RELISH consortium members have access to a shared letterhead template, business cards, deliverable templates, and a press release template. In M7, UDUR will also produce a poster and presentation template, and contract design of a banner to prepare for disseminating ongoing or completed product activities and exhibitions.

Templates and communication or promotional materials for print and digital use ensure consistent RELISH identity and affiliation, all stored and accessible on its project management platform.

3.4.1 Stationary

Printable and digital stationary were contracted and designed, including a customisable letterhead and small promotional business cards with links to the RELISH Cordis page, website, and social media platforms.

Figure 6: RELISH customisable letterhead template

Figure 7: RELISH general informational/business cards

3.4.2 Report templates

Templates were created and shared to consortium members for submitting deliverable and milestone reports. The templates include styles guides and formatting (headings, body text, title page and titles, tables, captions) and project/EC logos.

Figure 8: Deliverable Microsoft Word template, 1/3.

Figure 9: Deliverable Microsoft Word template, 2/3.

Figure 10: Deliverable Microsoft Word template, 3/3.

3.4.3 Press releases

A standard press release template is available for all partners. Currently, the template is translated into Catalan and Spanish; when needed, it will also be translated into Italian and French.

4 Dissemination Channels

Disseminating RELISH project findings in academic, public, industry, and policy venues will help in building awareness of the project, potential impact, and policy or teaching guidelines.

4.1 Events

During the granting period, consortium members will participate and showcase RELISH project activities and outcomes at conferences, events, and exhibitions. Conferences and exhibitions have been identified or will be organised by consortium members (see Table 3). Consortium members will also explore other opportunities to

reach multiple potential stakeholders in the form of organizing paper panels, workshops, seminars, and food and cooking events.

Table 3: Planned RELISH consortium member event participation and presentations.

EVENT TYPE	DESCRIPTION	TARGET AUDIENCE
Policy workshops and meetings	Planned meetings between consortium members and policymakers on EU intangible cultural heritage (ICH) and AI-integration	EU policymakers and legal reps
Academic conferences	<p>Paper presentations at established and new food-related interdisciplinary academic annual (or intermittent) conferences</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oxford Food Symposium (Oxford 2025; 2027)) - Association for the Study of Food and Society/Agriculture, Food, and Human Values Society (ASFS/AFHVS) (Corvallis, US, 2025; Burlington, US, 2026) - Food on the Edge (Galway, Ireland, 2025; 2026; 2027) annual conference - International Conference on Culinary Arts and Science (ICCAS) annual conference - The International Association for the Advancement of Teaching and Research in Intellectual Property (ATRIP) annual conference (Copenhagen, Denmark 2025; Location TBD 2026; 2027) - The European Institute for Food History and Cultures (IEHCA) annual conference (Tours 2026, 2027) - Perugia (Umbra Institute) biennial Food Studies and Sustainability conference (Perugia, Italy, 2026) - Congress of the International Society for Ethnology and Folklore (SIEF) biennial (Location TBD, 2027) 	Academics, visiting stakeholders; international NGO reps
Methodology workshops and RELISH-organised meetings	<p>Invited and open call workshops with food studies scholars on recipe integration into teaching and research</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UNISG (Pollenzo), 2025 - Durham University RELISH meeting, 2026 	<p>Social sciences and humanities scholars</p> <p>Food studies students</p>
Exhibitions and forums	<p>Booth, talks, and presentations at food-related exhibitions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Terra Madre – Salone del Gusto (Turin, Italy, 2026) 	International public, including young adults, professionals, researchers,

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Madrid Fusión (Madrid, Spain, 2026 & 2027) - Gastronomic Forum (Barcelona, Spain, 2026 & 2027) - San Sebastián Gastronomika (San Sebastián 2025, 2026 & 2027) 	<p>polymakers, industry reps</p>
Hybrid online seminars and webinars	<p>Participation or presentation at organised seminar series</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Culinary Mind (UMIL), 2025–27 	<p>Interdisciplinary scholars, researchers and public intellectuals</p>
Invited local/regional talks	<p>Participation and presentation at invited local or regional events.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Theoretical Frontiers and Methodological Challenges in Food Services Marketing (Durham, 2025) 	<p>Scholars, general public, food professionals and industry reps, policy makers</p>

Thus far, UDUR has participated in several preliminary presentations and attended conferences presenting and promoting RELISH to multi-disciplinary audiences, including:

- Paper presentation, “Around the Table: Food, Language and Cultural Diplomacy in the Iberian Context,” Georgetown University (Washington DC, USA), February–March 2024
- Invited talk, Brown University (Rhode Island, USA), March 2025
- Invited talk, University of British Columbia (Vancouver, CANADA), March 2025
- Invited talk, Bryn Mar College (Pennsylvania, USA), March 2025
- Invited talk, “Theoretical Frontiers and Methodological Challenges in Food Services Marketing,” Durham (UK), May 2025
- Paper presentation, ASFS/AFHVS, Corvallis (Oregon, USA), June 2025
- Invited talk, “Food & Drink Networking Event,” Sheffield (UK), July 2025
- RELISH promotion, Oxford Food Symposium, Oxford (UK), July 2025

4.2 Publications

Several publications for academic, specialist and public readers have been planned to report on or collate literature and findings on specific WP-research and activities, as well as general RELISH approaches and frameworks. Consortium members’ will also explore other academic and the public venues to disseminate RELISH approaches and findings.

Table 4: Identified journals, presses, and online publications for RELISH dissemination activities and output.

PUBLICATION	DESCRIPTION AND EXPECTED IMPACT
<i>Intellectual Property Quarterly</i> (Sweet & Maxwell)	<i>IPQ</i> is a leading journal on the discussion of legal and policy issues relating to intellectual property law.
<i>European Intellectual Property Review</i>	For over 40 years <i>EIPR</i> has provided the most comprehensive coverage and analysis of the latest IP case law and legislative developments in the UK and internationally.
<i>Food, Culture and Society</i>	The official journal of the Association for the Study of Food and Society and, as such, one of the main journals in food studies.
<i>Journal of Cultural Heritage</i>	A leading journal devoted to studying problems concerning the conservation and awareness of cultural heritage in a wide framework
<i>Synthese</i>	A generalist journal of philosophy, it is Google Scholar's highest-ranking journal in the "Philosophy" category.
<i>Food and History</i>	The leading specialised journal in Europe in the field of food history. <i>Food & History</i> aims at presenting, promoting and disseminating research that focuses on food from a historical perspective.
<i>Appetite</i>	This journal publishes papers in many different disciplines around the food behaviour sector and is one of the most famous ones in this area.
<i>Gastronomica: The Journal for Food Studies</i>	Published by University of California Press, <i>Gastronomica</i> is a peer-reviewed, interdisciplinary, international journal publishing critical, translational studies on food. It is the go-to resource for understanding the social, cultural, and historical dimensions of food.
<i>Nature Food / One Earth</i>	<i>Nature Food</i> is a monthly online journal publishing top-tier original research, reviews, comments and opinions on the theme of food, crossing the disciplines of food-related research in the natural, applied and social sciences. <i>CITY</i> aims to publish outcomes in these high impact, high readership journals.
<i>Geoforum</i>	<i>Geoforum</i> is a leading international, inter-disciplinary journal publishing innovative research and commentary in human geography and related fields. It is global in outlook and integrative in approach. The broad focus of <i>Geoforum</i> is the organisation of economic, political, social and environmental systems through space and over time.
Edited Volume RELISH	An edited volume to be published open access by a first-rate academic press toward the end of RELISH, prepared by WP5 based on its 2025 methodology workshop in Pollenzo, Italy. The volume will be prepared by WP5 and will provide a state-of-the-art definition of the place and value for social innovation of recipes in European cultural heritage.

The StopGap

The StopGap is an editorial website and general-interest blog that updates a few times a week, with occasional posts by guest writers.

Current publications by consortium members related to RELISH activities and frameworks:

- Borghini, Andrea and Nicola Piras. 2025. “Semantic and philosophical approaches for advancing the identification and measurement of food waste.” *Nature Food* 6 (6): 547–552
- Tavakoli, Sahar. 2025. “Expiration Dates: Tschisi Eis.” *The StopGap*, June 4. <https://www.thestopgap.net/expiration-dates-one/>
- Tavakoli, Sahar. 2025. “Expiration Dates: El Bulli.” *The StopGap*, June 17. <https://www.thestopgap.net/expiration-dates-el-bulli/>

4.3 RELISH Stakeholder Network

RELISH will build a network of food stakeholders, scholars, and policy or lawmakers representing significant EU and international proponents of food, heritage, and recipe interpretation, including but not limited to:

- Slow Food International, EIT Food, Sustainable Restaurant Association, Guild of Food Writers, the National Museum of Ireland Country Life, OECD, WHO, FAO, EU Food Policy Coalition, FoodDrinkEurope, European Food Banks Federation, WWF EU, Safe Food Advocacy Europe, IPES–Food, European Commission; European parliament, European Environment and Sustainable Development Advisory Councils Network (EEAC Network), Barilla Centre for Food & Nutrition Foundation, Re-Imagine Europa, The Institute of Food Science and Technology, ICLEI – Local Governments for Sustainability, European Alliance for Plant-based Foods (EAPF), The European Public Health Alliance, Aprifel, politico, Farm Europe, Danone, Alpro foundation, The European Consortium for Political Research, The European Consumer Organisation (BUEC), Philea-Philanthropy Europe Association, A European Association for Agroecology, Friends of the Earth Europe, ACT Alliance EU, European Environmental Bureau, The European Food Information Council (EUFIC), Eurocities, Feedback EU, World Economic Forum, Pesticide Action Network Europe (PAN Europe), FoodTank, ClientEarth, IDDRI, The European Liberal Forum, Standing Committee on Agricultural Research, Compassion in World Farming, Milan Urban Food Policy Pact, European Vegetarian Union, etc.

5 Exploitation Activities

This section defines the framework and plans for exploiting and generating impact during and after RELISH's granting period, as well as the management of IP in project activities. These plans will be updated periodically as members continue to generate pathways to invest stakeholders and identify potential exploitability not yet represented below.

In relation to the development of the exploitation component of the DEC plan, exploitation activities refer to how WP partners will individually exploit their results, and also how the consortium will jointly exploit RELISH. Each partner is asked to provide details on their individual exploitation plans and to meet and develop Key Exploitation Results (KERs) in preparation for the revised DEC Plan (D11.1). Feedback and exploitation plans are ongoing through RELISH's enrolment in Horizon Europe's Results Booster programme.³

5.1 Definitions

Following the European Commission guidelines, exploitation entails:

“The use of results in developing, creating and marketing or improving a product or process, or in creating and providing a service in standardisation activities or shaping a policy. Exploitation can be commercial, societal, political, or aimed at improving public knowledge and action. It also includes recommendations for policy making through feedback to policy project partners or facilitating uptake by others e.g. through making results available under open licences. Exploitation focuses on the actual use of the results, translating research concepts into concrete solutions that have a positive impact on the public's quality of life.”⁴

When making use of results, RELISH integrates plans to recognise and identify exploitable results, forming partnerships within consortium members to develop these results within and beyond the lifetime of the project, identifies and reaches potential and existing stakeholder communities and institutions, and develops actionable and useful guides, frameworks, and communications on the applicability and impact of project activities.

Within project activities there are three outputs relevant to exploitability:

³ Funded by the European Commission under Horizon Europe, the Framework Programme (FP) for Research and Innovation 2021-2027; https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe_en

⁴ “Dissemination and Exploitation of Research Results,” European Commission - Research and Innovation, November 7, 2024, https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/dissemination-and-exploitation-research-results_en.

RESULT

Within this DEC Plan, project results are those which are not reportable to the EC and do not have specific exploitation plans in place, but through their dissemination and communication, may generate passive impact(s). They are defined by the EC as:

“Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights.”⁵

INDIVIDUAL/JOINT EXPLOITABLE RESULT

Individual or joint exploitable results are those where partners and collaborations within RELISH identify and actively plan to exploit throughout the life of the project. A preliminary table is provided in section 5.4. These will be revised and refined in preparation for identifying KERs.

KEY EXPLOITABLE RESULT (KER)

As defined by the EC (H2020), a Key Exploitable Result (KER) is:

“[A]n identified main interesting result [...] which has been selected and prioritised due to its high potential to be ‘exploited’ – meaning to make use and derive benefits – downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research or education.”⁶

Within the RELISH project, we will generate a list of KERs by the midpoint of the project, which will be prioritised based on their high degree of innovation, exploitability, and impact.

KERs will be selected based on their use and consortium member commitment to exploit during and after the granting period.

5.2 Exploitation methodologies

Prior to Month 18, RELISH will use several methods to identify KERs, develop KER exploitation plans, and track exploitation and impact.

⁵ “Glossary.”

⁶ European IP helpdesk, “Introducing the Horizon Results Platform and Horizon Results Platform TV,” Horizon Results Platform (European Commission), 10, <https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-02/HEU%20Results%20platform.pdf>.

First, WP10/11, with input from consortium members, compiled a table of potential exploitable results (see Table 6), which also identifies which WP teams contributed to the deliverables that have high potential to be developed into exploitable results.

Second, WP10/11, with input from consortium members, created a shared set of target audience groups to categorise specific stakeholders. The table breaks down identified user roles and preliminary RELISH messaging (see Table 1), grouped as: 1) Policymakers; 2) Emerging Adults; 3) Culinary Guardians, including a) Knowledge Guardians and b) Professional Guardians; and 4) Mediators, including a) Cultural Mediators and b) Educational Mediators. How these target audiences are allocated as *early-adopters* (those who are ready to invest in the results first), *end-users* (those who will use the results), and *beneficiaries* (those who benefit from the presence of the results in the world) in exploitation plans will depend on the result to be exploited.

Third, WP10/11 will schedule a series of meetings to guide WP Leads and their teams on selecting one or two results that have the most exploitable potential and which they will commit to exploiting after the granting period. Each team will be trained on how to employ the Value Proposition Canvas (VPC) to assess exploitability and use models (see 5.2.1).

Finally, WP10/11 will track the impact and use of KERs using a combination of qualitative (e.g. feedback or description of KER use, publication reviews, selection in teaching syllabi, integration in programmes, etc.) and quantitative metrics (e.g. publication citations, reproductions or growth of similar models or framework, etc.). Consortium members will report on exploitation activities to WP10/11 during and after the project.

5.2.1 Value Proposition Canvas (VPC) methodology

A VPC maps out a customer type related to a product or service offered by a business or organisation and how a product or service concretely addresses a customer's desires and struggles ("gains" and "pains").

We have adjusted the VPC methodology (see Figure 11) to reflect RELISH's output in providing social and knowledge transitions (rather than products or services) for "stakeholders" through concrete outputs, or "innovations" (e.g. new legal or policy standards, teaching guidelines, educational platforms, Open Access data repositories, and publications).

For each identified potential KER, WP10/11 will lead a meeting with relevant consortium members to fill out and finalise their VPC by M18.

Figure 11: VPC value and stakeholder maps.

5.3 IP management

Partners will have a proactive policy to protect IP. The support of exploitation and securing of Intellectual Property (IP) rights will be managed in accordance with the Consortium Agreement (CA) signed by all partners. This outlines how partners will share access to IP generated during the project according to the basic IPR rules defined in the Grant Agreement. All IP is owned by the partners who generate it. In case of joint creation, partners will enter into an agreement detailing the rights and strategy for exploitation and the ownership of shares according to individual contributions. All partners will have access to IP generated in the project if they need it to carry out their project tasks.

5.4 Timeline for exploitation

The tasks implemented in the timeline for RELISH's granting period are managed by WP 10/11. Within its WP tasks, plans and output related to exploitation, including workshops, reports, and meetings are outlined below in Table 5.

Table 5: Timeline for exploitation plans.

TASK	DESCRIPTION	MONTHS
T10.2	DEC Plan developed and submitted to EC; Preliminary exploitation plan and impact assessment outlined with consortium member input	M2-6
T10.2	Booster programme developing KERs, impact, and consortium member input	M5-8
T10.3	Creating channels for capacity building and policy input through involvement of regulatory and public bodies (e.g., European Commission, UNSECO, European Environmental Agency, as well as National food safety and regulatory bodies) through workshops and meetings co-ordinated via FA in WP3, UNISG in WP5 and UA in WP9.	M1-18
T10.4	1st exploitation workshop (first consortium meeting, Barcelona, February 2025). Workshop focussed on individual partners' results within the project. This will include defining products, processes and services resulting from the project, particularly those having commercial or industrial potential, as well as research outputs for publication.	M2
T10.4	Internal exploratory individual and joint exploitation meetings with consortium members and WP Leads to identify KERs and train on VPC.	M9-18
T11.1	Revised and submitted DEC Plan with results from first workshop and internal exploratory individual/joint exploitation meetings and Booster development.	M20
T11.4	2nd exploitation workshop at full consortium meeting (Pollenzo) presenting updated individual and joint results and IP protections. This will include defining the flow of IP between the partners and ownership and access rights as well as an assessment of further exploitation channels for results and reviewing the improved exploitation plan.	M20
T11.4	3rd exploitation workshop at full consortium meeting (Alicante) to agree the roadmap for the exploitation of project results beyond the end of the project. This will include cooperation models, funding methods for further deployment, main target markets, adaptation of project research results for broader application, and the identification of further opportunities, challenges and barriers relevant to the exploitation strategies. Information gathered from these three workshops will be collated into a roadmap towards the exploitation report.	M34
T11.4	Exploitation report on three workshops (T10.4 and T11.4) developed and submitted.	M34-36
T11.5	Policy roundtable with EU staff, led and coordinated by UDUR with contributions from consortium members (FA, UMIL, UNISG, CITY, UA, LYFE, RUC, UCC, ATU, BSC and IST). The roundtable will produce a report with recommendations.	M30

5.5 Exploitable results

RELISH members will pursue individual and joint exploitation of results. Before the midpoint project meeting and D11.1 submission, members will collectively identify which results, including KERs, they will develop and exploit after the project granting period.

5.5.1 Preliminary individual/WP exploitable results

Drawing from anticipated results in WP work packages and individual partner tasks, potential exploitable results were identified. More are expected to be identified and refined by M20 (D11.1).

Table 6: WP/joint exploitable results.

TASK OR OBJECTIVE	PARTNER	EXPLOITABLE RESULT
T3.2	FA, RUC, UMIL, UA	Shareable survey design on youth food practices
T3.3	LYFE, FA	New Open Access data from quantitative survey results on typicality
T3.4	FA, BSC, CITY, UNISG, UCC, UDUR	BSC report/research on methods and processes for visualising large datasets of recipe
T3.5	FA, ATU, RUC	Methodology and teaching tools for food memories/culinary workshop tools
T4.1; T4.6	UMIL, LYFE, ATU, RUC	Theoretical framework informing policy recommendations for ICH integration of culinary/recipe tradition (EU) (e.g. workshops and meetings)
M5.3	UNISG	Open Access edited volume (draft manuscript) on recipe methodologies (first of its kind)
T5.4	UNISG	Teaching with recipes video and textual materials
T6.2	CITY	Recommendations for leveraging IP (hard law) for soft law/sustainable food systems transformation
T6.3	CITY	Legal assessment of soft law instruments in comparison to hard law (report and publications)
T8.1	IST	Technical report on platform architecture, development and iteration
T9.4, T9.5	UA	Recommendations for policy makers, education, and cultural institutions on using EU recipes for cultural heritage, emphasis on

		grass roots/female-led orgs, empowerment and inclusion (developed from Ideation Workshop)
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5.6 Market landscape

Related to RELISH's innovative digital platform and collected recipe data repositories, WP10/11 and WP7/8 will compile examples of existing international and European culinary data collections and state-of-the-art platform comparisons.

Prior to D11.1 (M20), UDUR and IST, with input from all consortium members, will produce Market and Research Analysis on these comparisons and collections to identify KER competitive advantages for stakeholders and pursue data-sharing agreements.

Data repositories include but are not limited to: archives, free-licensed recipe repositories, private collections, cookbook collections. We have created a RELISH community in ZENODO, an EU-approved digital repository.

Digital platforms include but are not limited to: searchable recipe repositories, AI cooking companions, recipe and culinary visualisation apps and collections, and platforms for user-generated recipe or cookbook collections.

Competitive advantages will reflect RELISH objectives and be used to assess existing collections/platforms based on:

- Comprehensiveness—reflecting a wide range and fair distribution of geographic types
- Integration of non-technical or instructional data—for example, integrating and coding historical, sustainability and cultural dimensions
- Practicality—offering pathways for addressing learning barriers or gaps and sustainable practices
- Searchable—integrating multiple codes/categories in search bases, e.g. ingredients, place, historical elements, carbon footprint, etc.
- Interpretability—allowing multiple stakeholders to analyse unprocessed data and provide visualisation and interpretation guides or elements
- Accessible—removing access barriers to collections, archives and data to academic, industry, and public stakeholders
- Growth—enabling growth via adopter and user input, use and presence of new data

6 Conclusions

This document presents the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) Plan that will guide the consortium to maximise the project's impacts during and after its lifetime. The DEC plan includes the ongoing and next steps to take to achieve its stated objectives. The DEC plan will be updated regularly as the project progresses.

RELISH is currently participating in the EC's Booster programme. Its first exploitation workshop was conducted in M2 during the consortium's first in-person meeting in Barcelona Spain (February 2025). Exploitation plans, although preliminary at this point, are also on track and will be augmented and refined in preparation for the next revised DEC plan (D11.1, due M20).

Prior to M20, RELISH will continue focussing on and initiating the following dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities:

- Participating and presenting in academic conferences
- Organising and completing workshops, and webinars
- Populating the RELISH website, Digest, and social media channels
- Publishing short- and long-form pieces in online forums
- Publishing academic research articles and edited volumes on project activities, frameworks, and literature reviews
- Building a network of researchers, institutions, and projects related to food, recipes, and heritage
- Developing and refining the RELISH podcast
- Publishing press releases
- Involving potential stakeholders and end-users in planned workshops, seminars, and surveys
- Refining exploitable results and activities through regular scheduled consortium member meetings

